

*Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge,
H2020*

D5.6: Tool support for pattern exploration, composition and visualisation (V1.0)

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Project Information

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2	OU	THE OPEN UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
3	KCL	KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	United Kingdom
4	NUI GALWAY	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY	Ireland
5	MiC	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
7	CNAM	CONSERVATOIRE NATIONAL DES ARTS ET METIERS	France
8	NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID	Netherlands
9	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN	Netherlands
10	DP	DIGITAL PATHS	Italy

Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.6 is titled: *Tool support for pattern exploration, composition and visualisation*. It is due end month 36 (December 2023), extended to Month 38 (February 2024) by agreement. The lead beneficiary is NUIG. It is linked to Task 4 of WP5: *Pattern exploration, composition and visualisation*. It is a software deliverable. This document will briefly describe the software.

The role of this software in the overall Polifonia project is to serve as a demonstration and application of previous work within the project, especially in WP2, WP3, and the TUNES pilot. In TUNES, metadata on folk music collections has been linked and converted to knowledge graph (KG) format, taking advantage of newly-developed ontologies developed in WP2. Ultimately, the TUNES KG represents this data, adhering to the Polifonia Music Meta ontology as part of the Polifonia Ontology Network (PON). Meanwhile, in WP3, we have developed methods for extraction of melodic patterns, and the resulting pattern data is formalised in a Patterns KG, again linked to PON. The Patterns KG takes advantage of and lives “on top of” the TUNES KG. The Patterns KG contains information on patterns present in tunes, allowing tunes to be linked via common patterns. The role of the software being delivered here is then as a tool and user interface for musicologists, musicians, and lay users to interact with the Patterns and TUNES KGs

The software is comprised of a frontend (Javascript / VUE) and a backend (Python / Flask). Each is a component of the Polifonia ecosystem.

The interface allows a user to:

- search for tune by fuzzy title;
- display relevant metadata such as key signature and tune type (e.g., reel, jig, strathspey);
- show patterns present in a particular tune, and show tunes containing a particular pattern, leading to a network of tunes and patterns;
- show instead just a network of tunes, suppressing the patterns which cause them to be linked;
- view and listen to individual patterns; and
- link to external resources for given tunes.

These interactions will be described below.

The interface was co-designed and evaluated by potential users, and we briefly report on this process in this document also.

The software is open-source (in Polifonia GitHub) with an associated Zenodo release. The running application can also be accessed online: <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns>.

Document History

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Author(s) - Institution
V0.1	10/01/2024	Pre-release outline	James McDermott (NUIG)
V0.2	07/02/2024	First complete draft for release to reviewers	Rory Sweeney (NUIG) and Pushkar Jajoria (NUIG) and James McDermott (NUIG)
V0.99	27/02/2024	Addressed reviewer feedback. Added CQs and Requirements sections. Reworked to use full chapter structure. Added takeaways from previous work. More information on evaluation. Moved scattered conclusions into a single chapter.	As above
V1.0	29/02/2024	Submission to EU	UNIBO

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1 Software Component Information Tables

ID	https://zenodo.org/records/10698076
Type	WebApplication
Title	Pattern Exploration UI - Frontend
Credits	Rory Sweeney (NUIG) and Pushkar Jajoria (NUIG) and James McDermott (NUIG)
Description	A Javascript/Vue web app which presents a pattern GUI to the user
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-exploration-gui
Documentation	README.md
Release	V1.0
Licence	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007
Running Instance	https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.5

ID	https://zenodo.org/records/10698170
Type	WebApplication
Title	Pattern Exploration UI - Backend
Credits	Rory Sweeney (NUIG) and Pushkar Jajoria (NUIG) and James McDermott (NUIG)
Description	A Python/Flask app which interfaces between the frontend (above) and the Knowledge Graph via the SPARQL endpoint
Source Code	https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-explorations-backend
Documentation	README.md
Release	V1.0
Licence	GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE, Version 3, 29 June 2007
Running Instance	https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/api
Bibliography	
Related Deliverables	Polifonia deliverables D3.5

2 Introduction

The Patterns UI is a simple, modular piece of software for exploring a database of tunes and melodic patterns, stored as a KG. In particular it allows direct exploration of the graph as nodes and edges, with two different views, and for various types of search. It is attractive and, we have found, usable.

2.1 Background

The data to be explored in our UI is a database of melodic patterns extracted from folk tunes. (We have run with several different corpora, but the current version contains Irish tunes only.) Each pattern is an n -gram of integers, hence a sequence of length n which occurs more than once in the corpus. Several variant definitions have been investigated in our previous work, but for the current work we have settled on “accent-level” n -grams. This means that the tune is initially represented as diatonic scale degree integers, and then only those occurring on strong (accented) beats are kept. The familiar n -gram method is then used to extract all relevant patterns, together with a measure of their importance in the tune, based on a TF-IDF measure and a complexity measure. These have been described in detail in other Polifonia deliverables, D3.1-D3.6 [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

Further, the patterns are stored in a Patterns KG which itself takes advantage of the TUNES KG. The construction of these KGs is described in previous Polifonia deliverables, especially D3.4 [4], and draws on WP2 work in ontologies and KG creation [7, 8, 9].

2.2 Goals

Initially, the goals for the Patterns UI were not crisply defined. We began with the following key phrases in the description of WP5 Task 4, extracted from the Polifonia Grant Agreement:

- “[...] using the pattern detection algorithms developed in WP3 within tools supporting use cases in WP1
- ... Visualisation and exploration of musical patterns will be specifically emphasised
- ... enabling the user to combine navigation/exploration in networks of patterns (top-down view)
- ... expressive filtering and selection mechanisms taking into account knowledge associated to patterns through the knowledge graph (bottom-up view).”

Early conversations in the process were about defining goals rather than moving immediately to design. We took inspiration from previous work, and used a co-design process with potential

users, and the Polifonia Competency Questions data, to arrive at a set of requirements for the project. We then designed the software iteratively, and then moved to evaluation.

This document is structured to reflect the above process. We begin by reviewing some comparable previous work in Chapter 3. Then we describe the design / co-design process in Chapter 4, and software design in Chapter 5. The app is then described from the user's point of view, with screenshots, in Chapter 6. We describe evaluation of the software with potential users in Chapter 7. Chapter 8 contains notes on adherence to FAIR principles. We conclude with future work and exploitability in Chapter 9.

3 Previous Work

We have taken inspiration from several existing visualisations, UIs, and databases, both music-oriented and more general. Many of these have also been used both during initial discussion by the authors, and as examples during the co-design process described later.

Some important examples are shown in Figures 3.1-3.9. They are taken from previous within Polifonia and outside, from previous music user interfaces, and other domains. Each caption in this series of Figures points out an important feature which has influenced our design.

To conclude this review, it is clear that we will require search facilities over metadata and over contents; and an ability to show patterns on musical staves, and audition; and an attractive network diagram allowing exploration of relationships.

Figure 3.1: A harmonic relation graph, part of the Polifonia INTERLINK pilot and presented at the Sonar Festival Music and AI event in October 2021. Each edge represents an inferred relationship between a pair of pieces of music.

Maire Breathnach's

polka

```
X:7620
T:Maire Breathnach's
M:2/4
L:1/8
R:polka
K:Gmaj
B>c | dg cB | A2 AB | cd/c/ BA | G2 B>c |
dg cB | A2 AB | cd/c/ BA | G2 B>c |
dg cB | A2 AB | cd ed | dc B>c |
dg cB | A2 AB | cd/c/ BA | G2 B>c |
|:dg ga | =f3 e | dd d/c/B/c/ | d2 B>c |
dg ga | =f3 e | d/c/B/c/ dd |1G2 Bc :|2 G2 Bd ||
|: g2 f>d | cA A>c | BG G/A/B/G/ | AD FA |
g2 f>d | cA A>c | BG AD |1 G2 Bd :|2 G2 G/A/B/c/ ||
|: d2 dc | dg g=f | dg/A/ BG | AD FA |
d2 dc | dg ga | =fe dc |1 d2 G/A/B/c/ :|2 d2 d2 ||
```

Figure 3.2: The TunePal interface, <https://tunepal.org>, shows a traditional score with an abc score, side-by-side.

NLB070134_01

En_er_waren_eens_twee_zoeteliefjes

NLB070134_01

NLB072585_01

En_er_waren_eens_twee_zoeteliefjes

NLB072585_01

Figure 3.3: Results of tune similarity calculations by Peter Van Kranenburg, e.g. <https://syrinx.knorrie.org/~pvk/mgdp/20160321-n4-debugged/007/index.html>, demonstrating scores with similar patterns.

search for tunes ... [advanced](#) [help](#)

Walnut Gap TuneGraph - similar tunes (what's this?)

Found in Walnut_Gap from the Traditional Tune Archive abc collection

[browse similar](#) [search file](#) [search collection](#)

▶ 0:00 / 1:04

download: [abc](#) | [midi](#) | [png](#) | [musicxml](#)

Walnut Gap

Quick

Figure 3.4: The abcnotation interface, e.g. https://abcnotation.com/tunePage?a=tunearch.org/wiki/Walnut_Gap.no-ext/0001 demonstrates the visualisation of a small network of similar tunes.

Figure 3.5: The RISM search interface,

e.g. <https://opac.rism.info/metaopac/search.do?methodToCall=switchSearchPage&SearchType=2&emptyFields=true>, allows for advanced search in metadata.

Figure 3.6: A music similarity graph, from Ono et al. [10], including a zoom-in of a small section. The high visual complexity here demonstrates that show/hide functionality might be needed.

Figure 3.7: Screenshot from MusicLynx [11], showing an interactive artist page with a local relationship graph, based on shared categories.

Figure 3.8: The Neuma interface, <http://neuma.huma-num.fr/> and part of the Polifonia FACETS pilot, allows for pattern search with an on-screen keyboard interface.

Figure 3.9: The LOD Live interface, e.g. http://en.lodlive.it/?https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/place/municipality/00201_042002. This is not music-oriented, but served as inspiration for a live network diagram with show/hide functionality based on linked open data.

4 Design

This section describes how we went about designing the interface and software, incorporating potential users' feedback at early stages.

4.1 Wireframe Design

The initial phase of our project involved the task of designing the website's wireframe. This step was pivotal in laying the foundational structure of the website, ensuring that it was both user-friendly and tailored to the specific needs of our target audience - musicologists. The design phase also involved detailed planning of the website's key features, such as a search interface that borrowed elements from previous implementations while remaining flexible to accommodate various user input formats.

4.2 Co-design process

A significant aspect of our Co-Design process was conducting interviews with musicologists both within and outside the Polifonia ecosystem, including interactions with Naomi Barker (Polifonia), Aidan Thomson (external), Danny Diamond (Polifonia), Eoin Kearns (Polifonia), Seán Doherty (external), and Peter van Kranenburg (Polifonia). Initial wireframes and/or related interfaces were presented to the above researchers. In each case, this was followed by an open discussion with brainstorming about possible features. Sessions lasted 20-50 minutes.

The insights provided by these discussions into the practical applications and user expectations of our website were instrumental in designing such a user interface. For instance, Seán Doherty's positive reception of the network diagram as a method of interaction underlined its potential as a musicological tool. Feedback and minutes of these meetings are archived in the Polifonia Sharepoint (available to members of the consortium, and to the public on request).

Key takeaways included the need for a search interface leading to a list of results, the importance of visual cues like hovering and highlighting for information presentation, and the necessity of a flexible network diagram to explore and navigate the large corpus. Furthermore, these interactions emphasized the importance of catering to both casual and expert users, balancing immediate usability with the depth of information for more experienced musicologists.

4.3 Stories and Competency Questions

We drew on the existing Polifonia Stories and Competency Questions, stored at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/stories>.

For User “Brendan”, we seek to address CQs:

- CQ2: What tunes are similar to tune X, given similarity measure Y?
- CQ5: What are the metadata for collection X?

For User “Mark”, we seek to address CQs:

- CQ27: What are all compositions in tune family X?
- CQ28: What are the similarities / differences of all compositions in tune family X according to measure Y?

For User “Sophia”, we seek to address CQs:

- CQ3. What different motifs exist in a piece of music?

4.4 Requirements

Based on the above, we arrive at the following list of requirements:

- An About page with metadata, links, and explanations.
- A Search function, allowing search by different fields, including text fields like title, and structured fields like key signature.
- Fuzzy search to help deal with variant spellings of titles.
- Search by pattern, allowing different methods of representing a pattern (e.g., space-separated integers versus comma-separated).
- A Tune page, showing details of a particular tune, and relevant patterns, and linking to an external source.
- A Pattern page, showing details and relevant tunes of a particular pattern, and visualising a pattern on a staff, with the ability to listen to it directly.
- A Network diagram, showing tunes and patterns as nodes, with links representing a pattern present in a tune.
- A visualisation of tune family membership.

5 Implementation

We created a modular software design.

Our KGs were already hosted in a Blazegraph instance via a Polifonia-custom Flask app on a Polifonia server:

- URL: <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/fonn/sparql>

That URL thus provides a SPARQL endpoint. Communication to the endpoint is via SPARQL queries, similar to those on <https://github.com/polifonia-project/patterns-knowledge-graph/tree/main/queries>.

We wrote a backend server using Python/Flask to facilitate this communication.

Furthermore, we opted for JavaScript and Vue.js for front-end development.

Development was in GitHub. URLs are given below:

- Frontend: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-exploration-GUI>
- Backend: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-explorations-backend>

6 The App in Use

In this section we describe the final design of the app from the point of view of the user.

The interface offers a 'Search' page featuring three methods for finding tunes:

- A tune 'Title' search, which uses a fuzzy matching algorithm to enable searching using partial titles and misspellings.
- A melodic 'Pattern' search which searches for a melodic pattern contained within a tune.
- An 'Advanced' search which incorporates fuzzy 'Title' and 'Pattern' search fields, along with multiple-select drop-down boxes for 'Corpus', 'Key', 'Time Signature', and 'Tune Type', the options of which can be filtered using inputted search terms.

The search outputs the tune name and tune ID for each result, as well as relevant metadata such as tune type (e.g. jig, reel, strathspey), key and time signature, as shown in Figure 6.1. Each search result is a hyperlink leading to a 'Composition' page dedicated to the selected tune.

An example of a 'Composition' page is shown in Figure 6.2. On the 'Composition' page, there is a network diagram which represents tunes as nodes, coloured by the tune's tune family and connected by edges to the slightly smaller pattern nodes in black, representing melodic patterns contained in the connected tunes. A node can be clicked to reveal additional connected nodes and double-clicked to navigate to the node's 'Composition' or 'Pattern' page. Nodes in the network diagram can be rearranged by dragging them with the mouse pointer, and the diagram can be zoomed by scrolling. Two icons at the top left of the diagram allow for undo and reset functions for the visualisation. A 'Help' icon in the top-right corner of the visualisation, when clicked, displays a short series of tutorial panes that explain how to use the network visualisation. An example of one of these tutorial panes is shown in Figure 6.3.

A slider checkbox above the network visualisation allows the pattern nodes to be hidden, resulting in a network visualisation containing only tune nodes connected to other tune nodes based on shared patterns. This configuration is shown in Figure 6.4.

Additionally, the 'Composition' page features a panel on the left side listing the most common melodic patterns contained in the selected tune along with their occurrence frequencies. 'Trivial' patterns can be excluded from the list by adjusting a slider checkbox. 'Trivial' patterns are patterns with low pattern complexity. Pattern complexity is a measure of the importance of a pattern in a tune, defined as the proportion of unique note values in the pattern. For example, the pattern "5, 5, 5, 5" is very common in the MTC-ANN corpus. However, since it is repetitive, its pattern complexity is low, and so it is likely not a distinctive melody associated with that tune. It is de-emphasised thanks to the low complexity.

When a tune node is double-clicked to navigate to a new 'Composition' page, a middle panel is displayed, which lists the melodic patterns in common between the currently selected tune

Figure 6.1: The 'Search' page showing the 'Advanced' search interface. The 'title' field contains the partial title 'Maggie', which can match a number of tune titles as a result of the fuzzy 'Title' search feature. The pattern '1, 3, 1, 7' has been entered in the 'Pattern' field using hyphens as a delimiter. 'The Session' has been selected from the 'Corpus' drop-down. The 'Key' drop-down further limits the search to tunes featuring a Dorian key, and the 'Time Signature' drop-down specifies a '4/4' time signature. The results of the search are shown in a table below the 'Advanced' search form.

and the previously selected tune. Here too, trivial patterns can be excluded by adjusting a slider checkbox. The patterns listed in both panels link to their respective 'Pattern' pages.

The 'Pattern' page features a musical staff representing the melodic pattern in musical notation, along with a MIDI player that can play audio of the pattern. Below the staff, there is a list of the tunes that contain the selected pattern, each entry linking to its respective 'Tune' page. A screenshot of the 'Pattern' page can be seen in Figure 6.5.

The 'Composition' page shows the tune family associated with the selected tune below the page title. Clicking on this text navigates to the 'Tune Family' page, which lists all the tunes in the selected tune family. Each tune in the list links to its respective 'Composition' page. An example of a 'Tune Family' page is shown in Figure 6.6. The 'Composition' page also features a link to external resources for each tune.

Finally, the 'About' page provides information about the organisation and funding associated with the project, along with contact information.

Figure 6.2: The 'Composition' page showing, on the left, a table of the most common patterns in the selected tune, a middle panel containing a list of patterns in common with the previously selected tune, and a network visualisation on the right showing the current tune, some of its most common patterns, and other tunes that contain the same pattern. At the top of the page, the tune title and tune family name are displayed above a link to the original source for the tune and the 'Citation' button.

Figure 6.3: A network visualisation tutorial pane, opened by clicking on the 'Help' icon, showing an explanation of the types of nodes used in the visualisations.

Figure 6.4: The composition page featuring the network diagram with pattern nodes disabled. In this mode, the network diagram shows the selected tune and similar tunes based on the numbers of occurrences of shared patterns weighted by pattern complexity.

The screenshot shows the 'Pattern' page in the Polifonia application. At the top, the Polifonia logo and navigation links 'Search' and 'About' are visible. The main content area features the title 'Pattern: 1, 7, 1, 3' and a red 'Cite' button. Below this is a musical staff with a treble clef, a key signature of one flat, and a tempo marking of ♩ = 100. The staff contains the notes G4, A4, B4, and C5. A MIDI player interface is positioned below the staff, showing a play button and a progress bar at 0:00. Underneath the MIDI player, the text 'Tunes Containing the Pattern "1, 7, 1, 3"' is displayed. A table lists the following tunes and their IDs:

Tune	ID
Drowsy Maggie	S12407
Drowsy Maggie	S12414
Drowsy Maggie	S23242
Drowsy Maggie	S27945
Drowsy Maggie	S27946
Drowsy Maggie	S29583
Drowsy Maggie	S35491

The footer of the page is split into two colors: purple on the left with the Polifonia logo and 'Search'/'About' links, and red on the right with the text 'Knowledge graph Version: n-grams patterns-kg 1.0'.

Figure 6.5: The 'Pattern' page shows a musical staff featuring the pattern in musical notation as well as a MIDI player which can play audio of the pattern. Below them is the full list of tunes containing the selected pattern. Below the page title, is the 'Citation' button.

The screenshot shows the 'Drowsy Maggie Tune Family' page in the Polifonia application. The page title is 'Drowsy Maggie Tune Family' with a 'Cite' button below it. Below the title, there is a section titled 'Tunes within the Tune Family "Drowsy Maggie"'. This section contains a table with three columns: Name, ID, and Type. All entries in the table have 'Drowsy Maggie' as the name and 'reel' as the type. The IDs range from S12406 to S27945.

Name	ID	Type
Drowsy Maggie	S12406	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12407	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12408	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12409	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12410	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12411	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12412	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12413	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12414	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S12415	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S20867	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S21232	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S23223	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S23242	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S23248	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S24826	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S27	reel
Drowsy Maggie	S27945	reel

Figure 6.6: The 'Tune Family' page shows a list of tunes contained in the selected tune family. Below the tune family page title, there is the 'Citation' button.

6.1 Cite-as functionality and versioning

For academic reproducibility, it is important for a user of our system to be able to cite a particular search result or finding, as described in more detail in Polifonia deliverable D5.7 [12].

This is accomplished by rewriting the URL in response to the user's activity, so that the URL can be used as a direct citation of a finding. Not only resources such as tunes and patterns, and specific searches can be encoded in the URL, but also our composition comparison page which compares the patterns of two compositions. Typical URLs for citation are as follows.

Title search <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/?searchType=title&searchTerm=Lord>

Pattern search <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/?searchType=pattern&searchTerm=1,+1,+1,+1>

Advanced search <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/?searchType=advanced&pattern=2,+3,+1,+5&title=Lord&corpus=The+Session&key=Gmajor&timeSignature=4/4&timeSignature=2/4&tuneType=reel>

Composition page <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/composition/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F13430>

Composition Page with pattern comparison to previously selected composition
<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/composition/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F1029/thesession20211212%2FMusicEntity%2F13430/Lord%20McDonald's>

Tune family page <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/family/Lord%20McDonald's>

Pattern page <https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/patterns/pattern/2,%203,%201,%205,%203>

The 'Cite' button, found on the 'Pattern', 'Composition', and 'Tune Family' pages, reveals a feature that generates citations for the current page in a choice of 'APA', 'MLA' or 'Harvard' referencing styles which can be copied to the clipboard using the 'Copy' button. This feature in operation is shown in Figure 6.7.

To enable versioning, we have a footer showing the Patterns KG version string.

Figure 6.7: The 'Citation' button, when clicked, opens a panel displaying a citation for the current page, which can be rendered in the user's choice of 'APA', 'MLA' or 'Harvard' referencing styles. The 'Copy' button copies the citation to the clipboard.

7 Evaluation

We have run evaluations with 2 external users. We took advantage of good practice in evaluation thanks to the evaluation activities of WP5, especially D5.1 [13].

- Subject 1 is a PhD student, working on musical complexity and patterns, and music generation, working on both Irish and Iranian melodic music. Subject 1 is based in University of Galway but is not part of Polifonia. Evaluation took place 1 February 2024.
- Subject 2 is an experienced music / music technology researcher, working as a lecturer in TU Dublin, not connected to Polifonia. Evaluation took place 16 February 2024.

For each evaluation, the Subject was given a very brief explanation of the UI and KGs - tunes, patterns, links between them, and searches. The Subject was then given several tasks to be carried out, while two observers watched, made notes, answered Subject's questions, and gave hints, only when needed. The tasks given to the Subjects were derived from our co-design process, competency questions, and requirements, as described in previous chapters. They were as follows.

Given the tune title *Sleepy Maggie*, find two patterns contained in it The title was given orally, so Subjects were not given the spelling. But with fuzzy search, the tune was found immediately. Subjects identified the patterns easily and recognised that they were ordered by occurrences.

Given the same tune, find another tune with a pattern in common This is the crucial "linking" step made possible by use of linked data. Both subjects found this manageable.

Given a tune title, find the tune family Again, fuzzy search allowed the tune to be found. For Subject 1, finding the tune family (by hovering over the tune node to wait for a tooltip) was not obvious and had to be explained. The tune family name is also present in the top-left of the tune page, but is not prominent and was not noticed. For Subject 2, the tune family name in the top-left was apparent.

Find another tune in the same tune family Once the tune family page was found as above, this was trivial.

Find a tune in a major scale, in 4/4 time, in the *barndance* form Subject 1 was able to use advanced search immediately, but specifying A major, no such tunes were found. They quickly discovered that multiple major keys could be specified at once in the advanced search, fulfilling the task. Subject 2 quickly found the advanced search and knew what to do. After some hesitation, they were able to select all major keys.

Given a tune, find more tunes that contain the most popular patterns in the original This was trivial for Subject 1. For Subject 2, this was attempted by clicking on a pattern, which

did not work because the particular pattern was not present in any other tunes. The red flash indicator was not obvious to this Subject.

Use the network to find patterns in common between two tunes With some exploration this was accomplished successfully. During this exploration the difference between double-click and single-click in the pattern and tune network was an issue. It was not obvious that both exist and are different (single-click requests more patterns of the current tune, while double-click requests the tune page). For Subject 2, working via the network was fine, but they did not notice the second panel opening until it was pointed out. The panel's meaning was then obvious to the Subject. Subject 2 also commented here on the issue expanding and later "un-expanding" a node.

Given a pattern, play it This was trivial.

Given a pattern, find tunes it is present in Subject 1 correctly attempted this inside Advanced Search, but this was not working due to a bug (fixed immediately after). Observers directed Subject 1 to attempt this in Pattern Search instead, which worked.

Given a tune, find the original source This was not given as a specific task, but it arose during explorations. The observers had to point out the "more information" link.

Find the link to the Polifonia web portal (Subject 2 only.) This was not obvious as the relevant area of the participant's browser window was occluded by the online meeting software (Zoom control panel).

Identify the version string for the KG (Subject 2 only.) This was trivial.

7.1 Open demonstration and evaluation

During a Polifonia project general meeting, we held an open demonstration, which resulted in several observations and suggestions:

- The difference between different node and edge types is not obvious, and the difference between single- and double-click on a node is not obvious.
- Searching for a specific key works well, but searching for any major key, for example, requires some extra work. The suggestion is to allow for selecting multiple keys in Advanced Search, eg all major keys at once.
- The links on the web page to the Polifonia Web Portal and GitHub are not prominent / explicit.
- Concerning exploitability and reuse, it was suggested that some users might want to see code snippets such as SPARQL queries, and the URL of the SPARQL endpoint in use.

7.2 Updates

In response to the detailed user evaluations and open demonstration, we made several changes, including:

- Added a simple inline help facility, demonstrating the main ideas, different node types and colours, and the single-/double-click difference.
- A more detailed About page, including links Polifonia Web Portal and GitHub, to SPARQL queries and endpoint.
- Allowing selection of multiple keys at once.
- Change to the order in which patterns are added to the network diagram for a given tune.
- Other, minor tweaks.

8 FAIR Principles

In this chapter we describe the approach to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles in respect of the components of this deliverable.

8.1 Background

This deliverable is a software deliverable, containing one component of the Polifonia Ecosystem. While producing this deliverable we observed the 'Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science', described in the Polifonia Data Management Plan, final version [14].

In accordance with common open-source practice we have developed our software in the open, in GitHub. GitHub provides findability and accessibility and long-term persistence.

A large majority of code is written in Python or Javascript, using common installation methods (conda, requirements.txt) and common third-party libraries such as the data conversion tool SPARQL Anything. This ensures compatibility with many other pieces of software in related fields. It also ensures that authors and researchers face few obstacles in learning from or contributing to our software.

Our data is stored in standardised, documented, common formats with certainty of long-term accessibility – principally a Knowledge Graph in the standard, plain-text `ttl` (Turtle) format. Thus interoperability and reusability are ensured.

The software has also been archived on Zenodo for long-term persistence of the specific version reported here.

8.2 Components

We list the two central components of this deliverable, according to the component type classification of the Ecosystem:

Component Pattern Exploration GUI – Type WebApplication

<https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-exploration-gui>

Adheres to Polifonia 10 rules for Open Science: R1 (in Polifonia GitHub), R2 (Zenodo), R3 (Portal or Server), R4 (Orcid), R5 (grant acknowledgement), R9 (FAIR principles and licensing). The component has been checked for compliance with the Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines [15].

Component Pattern Exploration GUI Backend – Type WebApplication

<https://github.com/polifonia-project/pattern-explorations-backend>

Adheres to Polifonia 10 rules for Open Science: R1 (in Polifonia GitHub), R2 (Zenodo), R3 (Portal or Server), R4 (Orcid), R5 (grant acknowledgement), R9 (FAIR principles and licensing). The component has been checked for compliance with the Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines [15]. (Note: other related components include the Patterns KG, which has been described in previous deliverables, especially D3.3-D3.4 [3, 4].)

9 Conclusions and Future Work

The UI is currently complete as per our design, but some items of work have been suggested for future work:

- After searching a pattern, it would be useful to highlight it in context on a musical staff, as shown in the Humdrum Verovio viewer.
- It would be good to allow multiple types of similarity relationships to be shown, such as alignment similarity and similar methods developed by Van Kranenburg and colleagues [16, 17], or relationships via co-occurrence in corpora.

9.1 Exploitability

The Patterns UI can be exploited for impact and future work in several main ways.

- The UI is intended to be used as-is by musicologists, and for this we will continue to demonstrate it to potential users within our network.
- Secondly, it is less intended to be used by casual users, but the combination of an attractive, interactive, animated network visualisation and traditional music which has many non-academic practitioners, allows the possibility of attracting users from this audience. To this end, we will demonstrate the UI at events such as university open days and the Galway Science and Technology Festival. At these annual events, hundreds of visitors, especially children and parents, visit our stand over the course of a day, and we can demonstrate music and AI technologies and games. A large proportion of the general public in Ireland are regular listeners or even players of traditional music, so it is likely to attract attention. Some of the children may be inspired to further study in computational approaches to music, while the adults could be a source of contacts, collaborations, and users.
- The UI could also be useful in teaching & learning about music patterns.
- Finally, it has been suggested in Polifonia meetings that the code and UI could be useful for exploration of more general KGs. The frontend code is largely written to be independent of the specifics of the KG, as it goes via a backend and SPARQL queries, thus a large degree of reuse will be possible. For example, it will be possible to adapt the patterns UI to visualisation of the ChoCo dataset for chord pattern similarity. This will be explored in the remaining months of the project.

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